

BEYOND THE CHECKLIST: BUILDING COMMUNITY AND CONFIDENCE IN THE POWRR PEER ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract – Digital preservation assessment is often seen as a solitary or institutional task - conducted behind closed doors, with limited support or shared reflection. The POWRR Peer Assessment Program offered a different model: one rooted in community, trust, and collaborative learning. Through a year-long process combining structured curriculum, self-assessment, peer mentorship, and cohort discussion, participants engaged deeply with core digital stewardship frameworks while building confidence and connection. This paper explores how the program created a supportive environment for interdisciplinary reflection and action, offering a replicable model for community-centered capacity-building in digital preservation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Assessment is often viewed as a final step in a digital preservation journey - an evaluative task conducted in isolation, where institutions measure themselves against technical standards and hope for clear next steps. But for many practitioners, especially those without strong institutional backing or technical expertise, assessment can feel more like a roadblock than a roadmap.

The Digital POWRR Peer Assessment Program offered a different approach—one grounded in trust, mentorship, and community. Over two year-

long cycles, six cohorts engaged in a structured curriculum combining readings, self-paced learning, cohort discussions, and peer mentorship. Participants completed self-assessments using the NDSA Levels of Preservation and DPC RAM, then conducted formal peer assessments using the NEDCC Digital Preservation Assessment Tool. These reports were built on shared goals and mutual understanding.

This paper examines the program's design and outcomes, with a focus on how community-centered models build confidence, reduce isolation, and turn reflection into action. In line with the iPRES 2025 theme of Tūhono (Connect), we offer this case study as a model for transforming assessment into a more collaborative, inclusive, and sustainable digital stewardship practice.

II. PROGRAM DESIGN & STRUCTURE

The POWRR Peer Assessment Program supported practitioners through a guided, community-based approach to digital preservation assessment. Rather than relying on one-off workshops or static checklists, the program combined structured learning, peer mentorship, and hands-on application over the course of a year. This approach helped participants deepen their understanding of core concepts while building trust, accountability, and confidence through sustained cohort relationships.

Each of the two program cycles supported three cohorts of six participants from diverse institutional roles and contexts. Participants received a \$3,000 stipend, and their organizations received a modest \$870 Tech Start-Up Fee to support digital preservation infrastructure. Recruitment occurred through open calls on relevant professional listservs, and through partnerships with regional sponsors, including the Association of Hawai'i Archivists, Northwest Archivists, Amigos Library Services, the Midwest Archives Conference, and the Sustainable Heritage Network.

The curriculum was structured around monthly themes - such as planning, storage, tools, policy, metadata, and advocacy - designed to establish a shared foundation of digital preservation knowledge. These topics helped ensure that participants could better understand the landscape of digital stewardship work before diving into self-assessment and goal-setting. Each month featured curated readings, webinars, and discussion prompts, along with self-assessments using the NDSA Levels of Preservation and DPC-RAM. These widely used, community-developed frameworks assess preservation maturity across core functional areas. Participants shared and discussed their assessment findings within their cohorts. In the second half of the program, they used the NEDCC Digital Preservation Assessment Framework tool to conduct peer assessments, choosing either a traditional model (interviews and written reports) or a lower-barrier "co-assessment" approach. Both formats emphasized mutual learning and flexibility.

The program concluded with public project showcases where participants shared reflections, institutional context, and feedback on the tools used. These recorded Zoom events, hosted by cohort mentors, fostered dialogue across the digital stewardship community. Participants also submitted written case studies capturing self-assessment insights, peer evaluation findings, and next steps - a durable capstone learning product and institutional artifact. A final program white paper, currently in development, will synthesize outcomes, participant feedback, and a deeper evaluation of the assessment frameworks used.

III. WHAT WE LEARNED

Across both program cycles, participant feedback highlighted a consistent theme: combining self-assessment with peer connection transformed uncertainty into clarity, confidence, and momentum. Rather than filling out forms in isolation, participants talked through challenges, compared approaches, and learned alongside others facing similar constraints.

Many had encountered the NDSA Levels or DPC-RAM before, but were unclear how to employ them effectively, or how to interpret and act upon results. The structured curriculum provided scaffolding, while the cohort model fostered a supportive environment for tackling complex ideas and barriers. One participant noted, "Having the time and space to learn with peers made it feel like I could finally make sense of these tools—and actually do something with them." Another shared, "My attitude about this part of my work has totally shifted. I now feel capable, instead of overwhelmed."

Peer assessments were often cited as the most valuable part of the program. Feedback from colleagues who understood the work - but weren't embedded in the same institutions - offered fresh insight and validation. "These have made a great impact. I have provided all my assessments and reports to my director, and we have set goals together," one participant shared. Another added, "We applied for - and were awarded - a grant to hire a digital preservation consultant... preservation is now a central part of our operations with a significant and doable trajectory." Writing assessments for others also deepened participants' understanding and sharpened their own planning. As one participant put it, "Just knowing what to really address and what specific tools to ask for helped a ton." This mirrors findings from Structured Peer Learning models in higher education, where peer-led instruction has been shown to improve learning outcomes, increase student confidence, and create a more supportive environment for skill development. [1]

Participants repeatedly emphasized the emotional value of the program. "It was comforting to talk to someone in a similar situation," one said. "I didn't feel like I was behind anymore." These reflections underscore a key lesson: assessment is not only

technical work - it's also emotional work. By embedding learning in a community of trust, the POWRR Peer Assessment Program created space for both. These insights also prompted deeper questions about the tools themselves. Are these frameworks truly adequate for smaller or under-resourced institutions? While that question will be explored more fully in the program's forthcoming white paper, one insight is already clear: in a field often marked by perfectionism and fear of "doing it wrong," participants valued assessment models that affirmed progress over perfection.

IV. ADAPTING THE PROGRAM

One of the most significant takeaways from running the program across two phases was the importance of structure. Phase 1 followed a more flexible, mentor-led schedule intended to give facilitators and participants room to adapt content and pacing to their needs. However, this approach led to confusion and uneven engagement—participants often expressed a desire for clearer expectations and more defined content. Between program phases, we used the built-in six-month pause to evaluate feedback and redesign the curriculum.

For Phase 2, we implemented a structured monthly schedule with defined themes, curated resources, and specific assignments. This not only improved clarity, but also allowed participants to better prepare, engage with materials more deeply, and feel confident in their progress. As one participant shared, "Having a monthly topic and focus was a really helpful addition. It kept us on track and made the program feel more grounded." While we had hoped to avoid being overly prescriptive, we learned that many participants entered the program with less baseline knowledge than anticipated, and that clear scaffolding was not restrictive, but empowering.

As intended in the original grant proposal, the POWRR Peer Assessment Program was developed not only as a capacity-building opportunity, but as a pilot model that could be replicated and adapted by others. We are excited to see this vision taking root: the Texas Digital Library is currently piloting a peer audit and assessment program inspired by POWRR, adapting key elements such as cohort-based learning, mutual review, and a structured timeline. [2] While other organizations have expressed

interest in launching similar efforts, the Texas Digital Library initiative is the first to be publicly announced - a promising sign that peer-led models for digital stewardship assessment are gaining traction in the broader field. These inquiries signal a growing recognition that assessment can be more than diagnostic - it can be developmental, relational, and empowering. We hope this trend continues, and we look forward to seeing how future adaptations evolve to meet different community needs.

V. IMPLICATIONS FOR THE FIELD

The POWRR Peer Assessment Program suggests that community-driven, collaborative models can meaningfully reframe how we approach digital preservation assessment. By embedding self-evaluation within a supportive learning environment, the program shifted the tone of assessment from intimidating to empowering; and in doing so, helped participants build not only capacity, but confidence and connection.

This model stands in contrast to common critiques of traditional assessment practices in libraries and archives. Often framed as top-down exercises in compliance, assessment can feel isolating, opaque, and emotionally burdensome, especially in under-resourced institutions. Many tools rely on technical language and rigid benchmarks that don't reflect the day-to-day realities of practitioners with limited staffing or funding. Others lack empirical validation or adaptability, making them difficult to implement effectively in diverse contexts. [3] Even when assessments are completed, they rarely include guidance for how to move forward, leaving participants with little clarity and few support systems for taking action.

POWRR's model offered a different path. It demonstrated that sustainable digital stewardship depends not only on technical frameworks, but also on relationships, mentorship, and shared reflection. By treating assessment as a learning process, rather than a test, the program helped participants engage more deeply with the work, connect their challenges to those of others, and imagine new ways forward. This incremental approach aligns with strategies demonstrated in other settings, such as the University of Idaho Library, where staff used NDSA Levels as a guide to develop scalable, tool-based workflows that advanced preservation practices

without requiring significant resources. [4] Similarly, The Postal Museum in the UK used DPC-RAM to assess their digital preservation maturity and create a practical roadmap for growth. Their experience highlights how even smaller institutions can use community-developed frameworks to support planning, prioritize improvements, and build confidence over time [5].

This approach is highly adaptable. Cultural heritage professionals across museums, community archives, and other memory institutions face similar constraints, and could benefit from peer-based frameworks that prioritize empathy, accountability, and mutual support. More broadly, the program reminds us that capacity-building must include emotional scaffolding as well as technical training. When we invest in both, we don't just build skills, we build resilience.

VI. CONCLUSION

The POWRR Peer Assessment Program demonstrated that digital preservation assessment doesn't have to be isolating, intimidating, or abstract. When paired with shared learning, mentorship, and community support, assessment becomes not just more approachable—but more impactful. As a pilot initiative, it showed how collaborative learning environments can transform individual capacity into institutional progress. Participants left the program with greater clarity, a stronger sense of direction, and the confidence to take meaningful action within their institutions. As one participant put it, "I have been able to determine doable next steps for my institution and have started implementing several of them already. The program gave me the confidence to push forward."

This case study shows that capacity-building in digital stewardship is most effective when it is human-centered and relational. As we look toward the future of training and assessment in our field, we encourage others to invest in peer-based models that foster trust, connection, and collective growth. Digital preservation is not just about keeping bits safe - it's about building networks of people who can care for them, together. We invite the field to explore new models of assessment, ones that center trust, collaboration, and the lived experiences of digital stewards.

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